

APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL CULTURE IN
FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article discusses the professional pedagogical culture, its components, the importance of the teacher's professional culture, the possibilities of developing the pedagogical culture, the personal and social interpretation of the professional pedagogical culture, the approaches that form the basis of the professional-pedagogical culture, and the importance of the formation of professional culture in future students. This article serves as a resource for the scientific and pedagogical community, students, professors, researchers, and school teachers.

Key words: culture, professional-pedagogical culture, values, social-cultural experience, social-cultural consciousness, cultural outlook, activity, creativity, active technological approach, humanism, professional maturity, pedagogical skills.

It is known that today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the process of humanization is being implemented at all stages of the continuous education system. The humanism of education is manifested on the one hand in its content, and on the other hand, it is realized through the pedagogical activity of the teacher. That is why, in the process of higher pedagogical education, the cultural studies approach to the preparation of future teachers for this activity allows for the creation of an educational system with a national character. Because any culture embodies the nation's best experiences and achievements. In this sense, the Uzbek people have a centuries-old, rich cultural arsenal. Future teachers should have the competence to clearly determine their place and position in the course of their future professional activities and to use the rich achievements of national and universal culture. The successful solution to the problem of the professional formation of future teachers from the point of view of cultural studies allows for the effective use of education.

The issue of the professional development of future teachers in the process of higher

pedagogical education based on the approach of cultural studies O. Abdullina, V.A. Researched by Slastenin, E.V. Bondarevskaya, and V.V. Gorshkova The formation of the professional and cultural image of teachers is reflected in the works of M. Kuronov. Experts emphasized the need to direct the process of training future teachers to the development of their thinking. Because the teacher's professional culture is reflected in his ability to think logically and find practical solutions to problems and mixed resistances, Therefore, the pedagogical culture of the teacher is interpreted and analyzed as a component of the general culture.

The teacher's culture is manifested through his pedagogical skills, professional competence, pedagogical technique, and technology use skills. That is why the teacher's culture is evaluated as a phenomenon that expresses his social maturity. A teacher's culture is his most important professional quality. The teacher's culture is manifested through his pedagogical-psychological knowledge, skills, personal qualities, aspects that allow him to establish an effective relationship with students, his behaviour with the members of the pedagogical team, communication, and dressing techniques. Most experts recognize the teacher's professional experience as the main indicator of pedagogical culture. Therefore, pedagogical culture is expressed in the assimilation of socio-cultural experiences created by mankind, the level of its application in pedagogical activities, personal achievements as a teacher, and striving for continuous improvement of one's activities.

Experts have assessed pedagogical culture as the embodiment of high professional skills and teachers' unique qualities, mastery of teaching methodology, and cultural-creative qualities (T.V. Ivanova). On the other hand, pedagogical culture is the level of manifestation of socio-cultural and pedagogical experiences achieved by mankind through the teacher's activity. Accordingly, the teacher's pedagogical culture includes the following:

- the ability to understand culture and justify one's own cultural views;
- the activity of being able to form cultural thinking;
- the ability to know the essence of cultural values and to feel and understand them;
- the ability to determine one's own moral position at the level of creative skill;
- the ability to evaluate cultural communication and cultural phenomena;
- the ability to process cultural didactic tools;
- competence to promote cultural ideas.

Professional pedagogical culture is a cultural pedagogical phenomenon aimed at analyzing the activities of learners. In this process, the teacher is engaged in professional pedagogical

activities of a cultural nature. Therefore;

1. Pedagogical culture is a set of professional qualities of a teacher of an integrative nature.
2. Pedagogical culture is a phenomenon that provides opportunities and conditions for professional activity.
3. Pedagogical culture is a generalized indicator of a teacher's professional competence.
4. Pedagogical culture is the goal of a teacher's professional self-improvement.

The professional-pedagogical culture of a teacher includes activities and conditions for self-presentation. Professors, teachers, and students demonstrate the unique manifestations of pedagogical culture in the process of implementing various regional forms of communication. Their actions within the framework of pedagogical culture provide opportunities for creating pedagogical values and technologies.

Our analysis shows that the pedagogical culture and the professional pedagogical culture of the teacher at the current stage of Uzbekistan's development are of great interest to specialists and the pedagogical community. Because the need to engage in interpersonal cultural relations in the educational process and in the life of society is becoming more urgent than ever, The professional-pedagogical activity of the teacher is especially important in expanding the scope of interpersonal cultural relations among the members of society. This need calls for equipping future teachers with the most necessary knowledge in this direction in order to form professional and pedagogical skills. Most approaches serve to reflect on the subjective forms of existing pedagogical culture. It is reflected in the description of the professionally important qualities of teachers, professional skills and competence, and the personal desire of teachers to improve their culture. However, these approaches do not allow us to interpret the pedagogical culture as an objective reality. Pedagogical culture should be reflected in the socio-pedagogical consciousness of society members and should represent the level of maturity of future teachers. That is why there is a strong need for the development of the pedagogical culture of future teachers in higher pedagogical educational institutions.

The methodological basis of the development of the professional and pedagogical culture of future teachers is the educational process of an integrative nature, and in this process, the cultural and historical pedagogical heritage of the Uzbek people takes a priority place. Axiological, active, personal-creative approaches that have emerged in cultural studies should be embodied in the professional-cultural competence of future teachers.

The teacher's professional and pedagogical culture also determines his attitude towards the

cultures of other nations. National and universal values form the basis of the highly developed professional culture of a teacher. In a word, the teacher's professional culture is the product of his creative activity. Based on values, future teachers shape and develop their activities. Accordingly, culture is the basis for inspiration for the future teacher's creative activity and professional achievements. Therefore, the high level of the teacher's professional culture is his independent creative activity. The teacher's creative activity is based on moral values.

Professional-pedagogical culture ensures the creativity and independence of the specialist. Therefore, the teacher's culture is interpreted as a product of his creative activity and creates a basis for a personal-creative approach. The teacher's creative activity is reflected in his professional pedagogical culture. From this point of view, culture is a measure of the creative development of a person. Accordingly, it is evaluated according to the extent to which a person communicates values. The interpretation of culture as a set of methods of activity forms the basis of a systematic technological approach to the teacher's pedagogical culture.

Approaches that serve to develop the teacher's professional culture should be reflected in the works dedicated to the research of this phenomenon. For this, it is required to expand the scope of research aimed at the formation of professional culture in future teachers.

References:

1. Slastenin V.A. And others. Pedagogy: Proc. A manual for students. Higher Ped. Textbook Establishments. – School-Press, 2006. – 512
2. Ivanova T.V. Business culture. Legal argumentation: textbook for secondary vocational education / 2nd ed., revised. and additional – M.: Yurayt, 2023. - 197 p.
3. Isaev I.F. Professional and pedagogical culture of the teacher: Textbook. aid for students higher textbook establishments. - 2nd ed., erased. - M.: Publishing center "Academy", 2004.- 208 p.
4. M. Kuronov. The system of educating a well-rounded person in the process of continuous education is a pamphlet. Tashkent: 2005
5. Kuronov, M. The definition of "spirituality" is a fundamental issue in the spiritual training of future teachers. Collection of materials from the international scientific and practical conference "Strategies for the development of professional competence of future teachers based on a cultural approach: problems and solutions," October 19–20, 2023 (T.: Science and

Innovation, 2023).